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Realising the potential of technology in education

EdTech in Senegal: A rapid scan

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Country Scan

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1. About this scan

EdTech Hub country scans explore factors that enable and hinder the use of technology in education. These factors include the policy or vision for EdTech, institutional capacity, private-sector partnerships and the digital infrastructure. The scans are intended to be comprehensive but are by no means exhaustive. However, we hope they will serve as a useful starting point for more in-depth discussions about opportunities and barriers in EdTech in specific countries, in this case, Senegal.

This report was originally written in June 2020. It is based primarily on desk research, with quality assurance provided by a country expert. Given how rapidly the educational technology landscape is evolving, the Hub plans to provide periodic updates. Table 1 provides a summary of the situation regarding EdTech in Senegal.

Table 1. EdTech in Senegal

Policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• 2016 Digital Senegal Strategy (International Telecommunications Union., n.d.)• Education Sector Plan (Ministère de l'Éducation Nationale, et al.,n.d.)
Infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Senegal has one of the highest levels of mobile access in Sub-Saharan Africa. In 2015, 93% of households had a portable telephone.¹• However, in 2018 only half of all primary schools in Senegal had access to electricity and 27% had access to computers for pedagogical purposes.²• In 2018, 67% of households had access to electricity (World Bank, n.d.-a)

¹ International Telecommunications Union. (2017), as available at <https://www.itu.int/en/ITU-D/Pages/default.aspx>

² UNESCO Institute for Statistics. (n.d.), as available at <http://data.uis.unesco.org/>

	<p>and only 24% had internet access (Central Intelligence Agency, n.d.). Data costs for using online resources are expensive for most of the population.</p>
<p>Partners and initiatives</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The National Education Information and Management System (SIMEN) and the School Radio and Television Broadcasting Division (DRTS) are two Ministry of National Education (MEN) agencies with core roles in EdTech. • The Ministry of Digital Economy and Telecommunications³ is responsible for developing and implementing the nation's ICT policy and strategy. • The Telecommunications and Post Regulatory Authority (ARTP) created in 2001, serves as the sector's regulator. • EdTech initiatives led by MEN focus on providing online resources for distance learning and supporting radio and TV education programmes. • Non-governmental agencies (USAID, Worldbank, TV and radio broadcasters) play a large role in funding, implementing and supporting EdTech initiatives.
<p>Covid-19</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • On March 14, 2020, the President of Senegal ordered all schools closed. • The Ministry of National Education has launched several initiatives to keep learning going for students. These initiatives include an Online Resource Centre⁴ designed to facilitate learning at home, including TV and radio programming. A distance learning programme⁵ has also been set up, with the objective of providing access to multiple options for learning, including via television, national radio, community radio, online and via mobile phone.

³ Ministère de L'Économie Numérique et des Télécommunications. (n.d.), as available at <http://www.numerique.gouv.sn/>

⁴ (Ministère de l'Éducation National. n.d.-b), as available at <https://education.sn/fr/article/230>

⁵ Senprof Education. (n.d.-a), as available at <https://senprof.education.sn/MIEUX%20ENSEIGNER%20EN%20FRAN%C3%87AIS/Compr%C3%A9hension%20%C3%A9crire%20vers%20le%20C1/>

2. Country overview

Since independence from France in 1960, the Republic of Senegal, a country in West Africa, has benefited from a history of peaceful transitions of democratic governments. Political stability has resulted in strong economic growth. The annual economic growth rate has stayed at nearly six per cent since 2014 (Universalia, 2019).

Despite strong economic growth and status as a lower-middle-income country, 38 percent of its 15.8 million population still live under US\$1.90 (2011 PPP US\$) a day (Universalia, 2019). Senegal's Human Development Index (HDI) value for 2017 is 0.505, positioning the country in the low human development category and ranking it at 164 out of 189 countries and territories (UNDP, 2018). Senegal's Inequality-adjusted Human Development Index (IHDI) is 0.340, ranking it 165 out of 189 countries (UNDP, 2018).

Predominantly Muslim (95%), Senegal is made up of over twenty ethnic groups, the largest being Wolof / Lebou (40.8%) followed by Pular (27.6%), Serere (14.4%), Diola (5.3%) and Mandinka (4.2%) (World Bank, 2013). Administratively, Senegal is divided into 14 regions, 113 municipalities, 370 rural communities and 14,400 villages (World Bank, 2013).

Senegal's long-term development vision is outlined in the 'Plan Senegal Emergent' (PSE) launched in 2013. It is based on three pillars:

1. Economic transformation
2. Human capital improvement
3. Strengthening good governance and the rule of law

The revised 2014–2023 PSE Priority Action Plan sets out an ambitious growth path for the country towards 2035. The plan is also aligned with the global Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and the Africa Union Agenda 2063 (Universalia, 2019).

3. Education system overview

The overall policy framework for the national education system in Senegal is outlined in the 2014–2023 PSE, which includes an overarching objective on developing human capital to support economic development (Universalia, 2019).

The overall management of the education sector falls under the purview of three ministries:

1. Ministry of National Education (MEN), which oversees pre-primary through to lower and upper secondary, as well as adult basic education;
2. Ministry of Higher Education, Research and Innovation (MESRI);
3. Ministry of Vocational Training, Learning and Handicrafts (MFPAA), which oversees TVET.

Senegal's formal education system is organised into pre-primary, primary (élémentaire), lower secondary (moyen), upper secondary (secondaire) and higher education, with TVET streams at both upper secondary and higher education levels.

Education is mandatory and nominally free for primary, lower secondary and one year of pre-primary. The official language of instruction is French. The four main levels of education in Senegal are:

1. Pre-primary: At least 1 year of pre-primary schooling for children aged 3–5;
2. Primary: Six years of primary education for children aged 6–11;
3. Lower secondary: Four years of lower secondary education for children aged 12–15;
4. Upper secondary: Three years of upper secondary education for children aged 16–18.⁶

The local education group (LEG) in Senegal, Groupe National des Partenaires de l'Éducation et de la Formation (GNPEF), is the main forum for education-sector coordination and dialogue. It includes a thematic group for development partners with three sub-committees, structured around ministry subsectors. The GNPEF has a plenary membership of 95 agencies, including representation by government, development partners, parent and student associations, academics, CSOs, teachers' unions, the private sector, and locally elected officials. The chairmanship of the GNPEF rotates annually among the three ministries (MEN, MESRI and MFPAA) (Universalialia, 2019).

Box 1. Extent of non-formal schooling in Senegal

An estimated 37 per cent of all children aged 6 to 16 are not enrolled in formal education (considered out-of-school). A large majority of these children attend Islamic schools, called *daaras*. Traditional *daaras* focus predominantly on teaching students to learn and read through memorising the Qur'an. Arabic *daaras* also provide Arabic language instruction in addition to memorising the Qur'an. Franco-Arabic *daaras* can be either private or public and provide instruction in Arabic and French languages and often also certain subjects used in public schools, such as reading, writing and

⁶ Global Partnership for Education. (n.d.), as available at <https://www.globalpartnership.org/where-we-work/senegal>

mathematics (Universalialia, 2019). Under the purview of MEN, *Inspection des Daaras* (ID), is the government agency that oversees education within daaras.

3.1. Education sector progress and challenges

Since 2010, Senegal has made substantial improvements in terms of access to education. Progress in this area can be linked to the Government's long-standing political commitment to expand access to basic education and reduce disparities, in particular related to gender (Universalialia, 2019).

Between 2012 and 2017, access increased at the pre-primary and upper secondary levels although considerable improvement is still needed. The gross enrollment ratio (GER) in pre-primary improved from 14% to 16.2% while the net enrolment ratio (NER) improved from 12% to 15%.⁷ During the same period, GER in upper secondary improved from 28.3% to 35.7%. The lower secondary completion rate improved from 34.1% to 36.8% between 2012–2017, but declined from a high of 40.5% in 2014.⁸

Maintaining high levels of enrollment and attendance for girls in primary education has been a significant accomplishment. The primary GER for girls has stayed around 90% since 2013. However, the situation has shifted with growing inequalities noted for boys in enrollment, repetition and completion at the primary and lower secondary level (Universalialia, 2019). The primary Gender Parity Index (GPI) has not decreased below 1.12 since 2013.⁹

Despite progress, challenges still remain. National data sets since 2010 have shown that most children in the first three grades of school are not learning to read at grade level. Low quality and inequitable service delivery have left youth lacking in opportunity and essential life skills (USAID, 2019). Analysis of annual school-leaving exams and national learning assessments show significant fluctuations in pass rates and scores over the past five years (Universalialia, 2019).

There are limited resources for non-personnel based expenditure as the majority of public spending on education is used to pay teacher salaries. According to the World Bank, "the government faces fiscal pressure as greater investment in education is needed to increase education access and quality (World Bank, 2016)."

The education system in Senegal is challenged by substantial inequalities that stem from geographic and socioeconomic disparities in access and quality. Although basic education is nominally free of charge, indirect and direct costs associated with schooling

⁷ UNESCO Institute for Statistics. (n.d.), as available at <http://data.uis.unesco.org/>

⁸ UNESCO Institute for Statistics. (n.d.), as available at <http://data.uis.unesco.org/>

⁹ UNESCO Institute for Statistics. (n.d.), as available at <http://data.uis.unesco.org/>

represent a significant barrier for many parents (UNESCO Institute for Statistics, 2014). In addition, one of the biggest challenges facing the sector is the large population of out-of-school (OOS) children between 6–16 years. An estimated 33 per cent of all children are not enrolled at the national level and significant regional and gender disparities exist (WAEMU, 2008). A recent report finds that “five out of Senegal’s 14 regions account for 56 per cent of total OOS children (but only 30 per cent of the national population) (Universalia, 2019).”

3.2. Education Sector Plan

The education sector is guided by the *Programme d’Amélioration de la Qualité, de l’Équité et de la Transparence* (Ministère de l’Éducation Nationale, et al., n.d.). The sector plan has three overarching objectives:

1. Dramatically improve learning outcomes at all levels.
2. Improve coverage, diversification and integration of the education and training systems at all levels.
3. Establish transparent and effective sector-based governance geared towards results.

PAQUET 2018–2030 builds on a strong tradition of education-sector planning. Over the course of the past decade, Senegal has developed three Education Sector Plans, covering the periods between 2000–2011, 2013–2025, and 2018–2030 (Universalia, 2019).

4. EdTech policy and strategy

In this section, we describe Senegal’s national ICT policy and include a brief look at the ICT in education policy.

4.1. National policy

The national ICT policy document is the 2016 Digital Senegal Strategy (International Telecommunications Union, n.d.). It calls for making broadband a priority by supporting public–private partnerships for infrastructure sharing and deploying networks in unserved areas. The policy’s ambitious “digital for all” vision seeks to provide broadband access across different areas such as schools, government services, and commerce by 2025 (International Telecommunications Union, 2018).

The Ministry of Posts and Telecommunications is responsible for developing and implementing the nation’s ICT policy and strategy. The Telecommunications and Post Regulatory Authority (ARTP) created in 2001, serves as the sector’s regulator. The 2011

Code of Telecommunications governs the ARTP's activities (International Telecommunications Union, 2018). 4.2. ICT in education policy

Senegal does not have an ICT in education policy. However, EdTech is a key strategic priority for the MEN and features in the 2018–2030 PAQUET. According to the education sector plan, the government aims to integrate ICTs to improve equitable access, the quality of teaching and learning, and governance of the sector (Ministère de l'Éducation Nationale, et al, n.d.). Specifically, the three strategic EdTech objectives are:

1. Build the capacity of all education personnel by (i) training in the use of ICT and digital educational resources; (ii) promoting new training tools such as (E-Learning system, distance learning tutorials, tablets, functional interactive whiteboards, virtual classes, etc.).
2. Improve the learning environment in schools and universities through ICT.
3. Improve the management of resources through ICT.

5. ICT infrastructure

Senegal has one of the highest levels of mobile access in Sub-Saharan Africa. In 2015, 93 per cent of households had a portable telephone (International Telecommunications Union, 2018). Ninety-seven per cent of urban households and 89 per cent of rural households had access to a portable telephone (International Telecommunications Union, 2018). Telecommunication reforms in the 2000s allowed new operators into the market which increased the supply of mobile services. Today, Senegal has three nationwide mobile operators: SONATEL, offering a service under the Orange brand, TIGO¹⁰ a subsidiary of Luxembourg-headquartered MILLICOM, and EXPRESSO, which launched operations in 2009 and is a subsidiary of SUDATEL, the incumbent telecommunication operator in Sudan (International Telecommunications Union, 2018).

Despite growth in the telecommunications sector, access to electricity, computers, and the internet in households and schools is limited. Only half of all primary schools in Senegal have access to electricity and 27 per cent have access to computers for pedagogical purposes. Less than 70 per cent of households have access to electricity and only 24 per cent have internet access. Data costs for using online resources are expensive for most of the population. It is estimated that less than 20% of senior students have access to online resources (UNESCO, 2020).

Table 2. Core ICT in Education Indicators. All 2018 figures from UNESCO.¹¹

Indicators	
Proportion of schools with a radio used for educational purposes (for ISCED level 1–3)	N/A
Proportion of schools with a TV used for educational purposes (for ISCED level 1–3)	N/A
Proportion of schools with a telephone communication facility (for ISCED level 1–3)	N/A
Student to computer ratio	N/A
Proportion of schools with Internet access	N/A
Proportion of learners who have access to the internet at school	N/A
Primary schools with access to electricity (%)	49.8 (2018)
Secondary schools with access to electricity (%)	76.9 (2018)

¹⁰ Rebranded as FREE in 2019

¹¹ UNESCO Institute for Statistics. (n.d.), as available at <http://data.uis.unesco.org/>

Upper secondary schools with access to electricity (%)	91.7 (2018)
Primary schools with access to computers for pedagogical purposes (%)	27.6 (2018)
Lower secondary schools with access to computers for pedagogical purposes (%)	60 (2018)
Upper secondary schools with access to computers for pedagogical purposes (%)	87 (2018)

Table 3. Other Key ICT Indicators.

Fixed-telephone subscriptions per 100 inhabitants	1.91 (2018) ¹²
Mobile-cellular subscriptions per 100 inhabitants	99.4 (2018) ¹³
3G coverage (% of population)	85 (2018) ¹⁴
Fixed- (wired-) broadband subscriptions per 100 inhabitants	0.82 (2018) ¹⁵
Mobile-broadband subscriptions per 100 inhabitants	N/A
Households with a computer (%)	11.59 (2016) ¹⁶
Households with internet access at home (%)	24.2 (2018) ¹⁷
Individuals using the Internet (%)	46 (2017) ¹⁸

¹² World Bank. (n.d.-a), as available at <https://databank.worldbank.org/reports.aspx?source=world-development-indicators#>

¹³ International Telecommunications Union. (2018), as available at https://www.itu.int/en/ITU-D/LDCs/Documents/2017/Country%20Profiles/Country%20Profile_Senegal.pdf

¹⁴ International Telecommunications Union. (2018), as available at https://www.itu.int/en/ITU-D/LDCs/Documents/2017/Country%20Profiles/Country%20Profile_Senegal.pdf

¹⁵ World Bank. (n.d.-a), as available at <https://databank.worldbank.org/reports.aspx?source=world-development-indicators#>

¹⁶ World bank. (n.d.-a.), as available at https://tcdata360.worldbank.org/indicators/entrp.household.computer?country=BRA&indicator=3427&viz=line_chart&years=2012,2016

¹⁷ International Telecommunications Union. (2018), as available at https://www.itu.int/en/ITU-D/LDCs/Documents/2017/Country%20Profiles/Country%20Profile_Senegal.pdf

¹⁸ World Bank. (n.d.-a), as available at <https://databank.worldbank.org/reports.aspx?source=world-development-indicators#>

Households with access to electricity (%)	67 (2018) ¹⁹
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¹⁹ World Bank. (n.d-a.), as available at <https://databank.worldbank.org/reports.aspx?source=world-development-indicators#>

6. Key partners and initiatives in EdTech

6.1. Government agencies

There are several government agencies involved in EdTech in Senegal. The table below describes their roles and responsibilities.

Table 4. Government agencies involved in EdTech

Ministry / Agency	Roles and responsibilities in EdTech
Ministry of National Education National Education Information and Management System (SIMEN)²⁰	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SIMEN is the central hub for data collection of education indicators and the agency responsible for overseeing the education management information system (EMIS). • SIMEN is also tasked with promoting equitable access to education data and to improving the quality of teaching and learning through the use of ICT.²¹
School Radio and Television Broadcasting Division (DRTS)²²	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The technical arm of the Ministry of Education that oversees the development and broadcast of educational radio and television programmes.²³
Ministry of Digital Economy and Telecommunications²⁴	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Ministry of Digital Economy and Telecommunications is responsible for ICT policy and strategy in the country.
Telecommunications and Postal Regulatory Authority²⁵	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Regulatory Authority for Telecommunications and Posts is an independent administrative authority, responsible for regulating the telecommunications and postal sectors.

²⁰ Ministère de l'Éducation Nationale. (n.d.-a). *SIMEN*, as available at <http://www.education.gouv.sn/fr/content/simen-0>

²¹ Ministère de l'Éducation Nationale. (n.d.-a). *SIMEN*, as available at <http://www.education.gouv.sn/fr/content/simen-0>

²² Ministère de l'Éducation Nationale. (n.d.-b). *Division de la Radio – Télévision scolaire (DRTS)*, as available at <https://education.sn/fr/standard/83>

²³ Diawara, R. F., & Sall, T. (2020), as available at <https://gemreportunesco.wordpress.com/2020/04/03/covid-19-how-senegal-intends-to-ensure-earningneverstops/>

²⁴ Ministère de l'Économie Numérique et des Télécommunications. (n.d.), as available at <http://www.numerique.gouv.sn/>

²⁵ ARTP SENEGAL. (n.d.), As available at <https://www.artpsenegal.net/>

Ministry of Higher Education, Scientific Research and Innovation (MESRI)²⁶

- MESRI supports the integration of ICT in teacher training processes and systems management in higher education.

6.2. Non-governmental agencies

EdTech initiatives in Senegal have been implemented and supported by a variety of non-governmental agencies. Donors such as USAID and the World Bank are supporting several large-scale education programmes that use ICT for continuous teacher professional development and are integrating ICT in classrooms to improve learning. UNESCO, UNICEF, UNHCR and ITU have developed a joint project to support the MEN's Covid-19 response plans (UNHCR, 2020). Private sector actors such as television and radio stations also contribute to the creation and dissemination of education content. Public universities like the Virtual University of Senegal support the Ministry of Education with the provision of digital teaching and learning materials and ICT-based assessments.

6.3. EdTech initiatives

Table 5 presents recent, large-scale EdTech initiatives in Senegal. Most EdTech initiatives led by the Ministry of National Education focus on providing online resources for distance learning and supporting radio and TV education programmes. The MEN has recently set up a system known as PROMEUT that aims to harmonise all online platforms in Senegal.

Box 2. Senegal's Covid-19 response

On March 14, 2020, the President of Senegal ordered all schools closed, making it one of the first sub-Saharan African countries to suspend in-person schooling. The Ministry of National Education has launched several initiatives to keep learning going for students. These initiatives include an Online Resource Centre designed to facilitate learning at home, including TV and radio programming. In late March 2020, the UNICEF office in Senegal received a GPE grant of US\$70,000 to support the Ministry of National Education with developing an education sector response plan. Senegal has used the funds for radio and TV education programming. On June 17, 2020, Senegal received Covid-19 accelerated funds (7 million USD) from GPE to support the national

²⁶ Ministère de l'Enseignement Supérieur, de la Recherche et de l'Innovation - Gouvernement du Sénégal. (n.d.) as available at <http://www.mesr.gouv.sn/>

Covid-19 response based on the national response plan. Agence française de Développement (AFD) is the grant agent for the Covid-19 GPE grant.

Table 5. EdTech Initiatives in Senegal

Initiative	Details
<p>Multi Partner Trust Fund (MPTF) Initiative²⁷</p>	<p>Overview: A joint UNICEF, UNHCR, UNESCO and ITU project that aims to support the MEN's plans to remedy the consequences of the closure of schools by deploying a series of distance learning solutions.</p> <p>Target group: Marginalised children and adolescents, such as those living in rural and remote areas with limited connectivity, in refugee hosting areas, and those with disability.</p> <p>Technology: Website, online resources, TV, radio</p> <p>Reach / scale: Nationwide</p> <p>Implementing organisations: UNICEF, UNHCR, UNESCO, ITU</p> <p>Government partners: MEN, Ministry of Technical & Vocational Training</p> <p>Status of implementation: Ongoing</p>
<p>Lecture Pour Tous²⁸</p>	<p>Overview: An early-grade reading programme that includes the use of ICT as part of continuous teacher professional development.</p> <p>Target group: Teachers, coaches and school inspectors in Diourbel, Kaffrine, Kaolack, Louga, Matam and Saint Louis.</p> <p>Technology: SIM cards, SMS, tablets, audio and visual materials, electronic coaching observation forms.</p> <p>Reach / scale: All public primary schools and 100 daaras in all six regions</p> <p>Implementing organisations: Chemonics International</p> <p>Government partners: MEN Direction de l'enseignement élémentaire</p> <p>Status of implementation: 2016–2021</p>

²⁷ UNHCR. (2020), As available at <https://data2.unhcr.org/en/documents/download/76898>

²⁸ Chemonics International. (n.d.), as available at <https://www.chemonics.com/projects/scaling-early-grade-reading-senegal/>

<p>Learn at Home²⁹</p>	<p>Overview: The government's main initiative to support learning from home. The initiative includes an online portal with a variety of teaching and learning resources to support distance learning. In its first phase, this platform will collect and classify digital resources and in its second phase it will be opened up to teachers, learners and parents.³⁰</p> <p>Target group: Teachers and students at all levels of education, and parents across the country.</p> <p>Technology: Website, online resources</p> <p>Reach / scale: Nationwide</p> <p>Implementing organisation: Ministry of National Education</p> <p>Government partners: Ministry of National Education</p> <p>Status of implementation: Ongoing</p>
<p>School TV (Tele-Ecole)³¹</p>	<p>Overview: Dedicated TV channel that broadcasts education programmes on a variety of subjects including mathematics, history, reading, English, etc.</p> <p>Target group: Students at pre-primary, primary, lower secondary and upper secondary school across the country.</p> <p>Technology: Television, online streaming with open access for all.</p> <p>Reach / scale: Nationwide</p> <p>Implementing organisation: Tele-Ecole</p> <p>Government partners: Ministry of Education</p> <p>Status of implementation: Ongoing</p>

²⁹ Ministère de l'Education Nationale. (n.d.-a), as available at <https://education.sn/fr/article/230>

³⁰ Diawara, R. F., & Sall, T. (2020), as available at <https://gemreportunesco.wordpress.com/2020/04/03/covid-19-how-senegal-intends-to-ensure-learningneverstops/>

³¹ télé-école. (n.d.), as available at <http://tele-ecole.tv/home>

<p>Senprof³²</p>	<p>Overview: An online portal with digital education resources on pedagogy, management and training for teachers.</p> <p>Target group: Teachers at all levels of education</p> <p>Technology: Online resources, digital books, Gsuite</p> <p>Reach / scale: Nationwide</p> <p>Implementing organisation: Ministry of Education</p> <p>Government partners: Ministry of Education</p> <p>Status of implementation: Ongoing</p>
<p>Education.sn³³</p>	<p>Overview: Online platform with educational resources for teachers and students. Allows users to benefit from various Google and Microsoft tools allowing them to work online. Teachers can access all of Office 365 and Google's G-Suite applications. Teachers can use Classroom, Google's free learning platform for schools and Microsoft's Office 365 online class platform.</p> <p>Target group: Primary, lower secondary and upper secondary school teachers, students and administrative staff.</p> <p>Technology: Online resources, virtual classrooms, software</p> <p>Reach / scale: Nationwide</p> <p>Implementing organisations: Ministry of Education, Google, Microsoft</p> <p>Government partners: Ministry of Education</p> <p>Status of implementation: Ongoing</p>
<p>Quality Improvement and Equity of Basic Education Project³⁴</p>	<p>Overview: Large basic education project that included ICT components to improve mathematics and science. Activities include teacher training on ICT use, integration of ICTs in the</p>

³² Senprof Education. (n.d.-b), as available at <https://senprof.education.sn/>

³³ Badiane, S. (n.d.), as available at <https://www.socialnetlink.org/2020/03/covid-19-au-senegal-pour-une-continue-pedagogique-le-ministere-de-leducation-lance-apprendre-a-la-maison/>

³⁴ World Bank. (n.d.-b), as available at <https://projects.worldbank.org/en/projects-operations/project-detail/P163575>

	<p>classroom for improved teaching and learning, and support for ICT-rich classrooms and schools.</p> <p>Target group: Primary, lower secondary and upper secondary school students and teachers.</p> <p>Technology: Digital content, hardware (computers) and IT support.</p> <p>Reach / scale: 230 pilot schools, 100 lower secondary schools (including BSTs), 30 upper secondary schools and 100 primary</p> <p>Implementing organisations: World Bank</p> <p>Government partners: Ministry of Education</p> <p>Status of implementation: 2018– ongoing³⁵</p>
<p>Education de Base (EDB) Project³⁶</p>	<p>Overview: Secondary education programme that included curriculum reform, teacher training, good governance and management interventions. Among other activities, the programme equipped school computer labs with hardware, software and internet connectivity and provided IT support; trained teachers in each school to be ICT coaches.³⁷</p> <p>Target group: Lower secondary students and teachers. Specific focus on vulnerable children.</p> <p>Technology: Computer labs, ICT infrastructure, online platform</p> <p>Reach / Scale: 10 of the country's 14 regions, including 350 daaras</p> <p>Implementing organisations: FHI360, USAID</p> <p>Government partners: Ministry of Education</p> <p>Status of implementation: 2008 to 2013</p>

³⁵ World Bank. (2018), as available at <http://documents1.worldbank.org/curated/en/176681527996626963/pdf/SENEGAL-PAD-05112018.pdf>

³⁶ Center for Education Innovations. (n.d.-a), as available at <https://www.educationinnovations.org/page/education-de-base-edb-program>

³⁷ Center for Education Innovations. (n.d.-a), as available at <https://www.educationinnovations.org/page/education-de-base-edb-program>

<p>TV programmes³⁸</p>	<p>Overview: Educational TV programmes supported by private television stations. Programmes include ‘Salle des Profs’³⁹ on TFM and “e-school” on the E-TV channel, among others.⁴⁰</p> <p>Target group: Primary and lower and upper secondary students and teachers.</p> <p>Technology: Television</p> <p>Reach / Scale: Nationwide, online</p> <p>Implementing organisations: Télé Futurs Medias, E-TV</p> <p>Government partners: Ministry of Education</p> <p>Status of implementation: Ongoing</p>
<p>Virtual University of Senegal (UVS)⁴¹</p>	<p>Overview: Virtual University of Senegal (UVS) is a public digital university, which aims to provide Senegalese youth with equitable access to higher education. Learning at UVS combines traditional classroom teaching with online training. UVS also supports thousands of students with teaching and learning materials and assessments.</p> <p>Target group: University level students, teachers and students in primary, lower secondary and upper secondary.</p> <p>Technology: Digital materials and assessments</p> <p>Reach scale: Nationwide</p> <p>Implementing organisations: N/A</p> <p>Government partners: Ministry of Education and the Information and Management System of the Ministry of National Education (SIMEN), (GEM, 2020)</p> <p>Status of implementation: Ongoing</p>

³⁸ Diawara, R. F., & Sall, T. (2020), as available at <https://gemreportunesco.wordpress.com/2020/04/03/covid-19-how-senegal-intends-to-ensure-earningneverstops/>

³⁹ Télé Futurs Medias (TFM). (2020, March 17), as available at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=kBROufYq6DY&list=PLdGjr0E0g2bPWLrnJ7-NsTfj3V7Bi4y0a>

⁴⁰ Diawara, R. F., & Sall, T. (2020), as available at <https://gemreportunesco.wordpress.com/2020/04/03/covid-19-how-senegal-intends-to-ensure-earningneverstops/>

⁴¹ Université virtuelle du Sénégal. (n.d.), as available at <https://www.uvs.sn>

7. Looking Ahead

Senegal is in a strong position to expand ICT in education initiatives. Mobile phone penetration rates are high and there is a general willingness of the government to pursue ICTs in education. The government is developing digital pedagogy and resources for teacher professional development, utilising ICT to support learning at home in response to Covid-19, and prioritising the digitisation of education data through SIMEN (World Bank, 2018). EdTech initiatives in Senegal can also benefit from broader government initiatives to develop the country's ICT infrastructure and position Senegal as an ICT hub for the West Africa subregion (International Telecommunications Union, 2018).

8. Further reading

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